

Position-Dependent Epoxidation as a Strategy to Tune Optical Transitions in Nanographenes: Coronene Model Insights

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the position-dependent effect of edge epoxidation on the optical response of symmetric nanographenes. Using coronene as a model system and DFT/MRCI calculations, we elucidate the mechanism by which the functionalization site governs the lifting of symmetry-forbidden transitions via substantial frontier orbital redistribution. The results establish a direct link between structural perturbation, spatial overlap, and photophysical properties, demonstrating that controlled edge modification offers a versatile strategy for the rational tuning of absorption and emission characteristics in nanographenes.

KEYWORDS

optical transitions; nanographenes; epoxidation; DFT/MRCI.

INTRODUCTION

Symmetric graphene quantum dots (GQDs), despite their high thermodynamic stability, exhibit limited optical and electronic properties. The high structural symmetry causes degeneracy of their frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) [1], resulting in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition being symmetry-forbidden [2].

Controlled functionalization represents an effective strategy for reducing the point group symmetry of graphene quantum dots (GQDs) and tuning their optical properties [3,4]. In particular, epoxidation—by altering the hybridization state of carbon atoms from sp^2 to sp^3 —can modulate the band gap width, thereby inducing a bathochromic shift in both absorption and emission bands [5,6].

However, our recent study [7] demonstrated that symmetry breaking induced by epoxidation can either render the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition allowed or leave it forbidden. The decisive factor governing the transition probability is the specific attachment site of the functional group. Nevertheless, the precise mechanism by which the functionalization position influences optical transition probabilities remains insufficiently elucidated.

The present study aims to elucidate how the optical response of graphene quantum dots depends on the epoxidation site. To this end, two non-equivalent edge positions in epoxidized coronene are compared—one exhibiting a marginal increase in oscillator strength, the other an anomalously strong enhancement. This comparative analysis reveals the mechanism by which the functionalization position governs the structural, electronic, and photophysical properties of nanographenes.

MODELS AND METHODS

Coronene is a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) with the chemical formula $C_{24}H_{12}$ and D_{6h} point group symmetry. Owing to its well-characterized nature [8,9] and high symmetry, it serves as a convenient model system for investigating the effects of epoxidation on the final properties of symmetric graphene quantum dots (GQDs). Furthermore, the high symmetry of coronene restricts the number of non-equivalent edge functionalization sites to two, thereby simplifying the comparative analysis. The structures of the epoxidized coronene isomers are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structures of epoxidized coronene isomers: (a) α -position, (b) β -position.

Geometry optimization of pristine coronene and its epoxidized isomers, along with calculations of their FMOs and vibrational frequencies, was performed within the framework of density functional theory (DFT) [10]. The hybrid B3LYP functional [11] and the def2-SVP basis set [12] were employed in all calculations. Dispersion interactions were accounted for using the DFT-D3(BJ) empirical correction [13]. Transition states (TS) for the transformation of the epoxy group into an ether bridge were also calculated to assess the kinetic stability of the epoxidized coronene isomers. The optical properties of pristine and epoxidized coronene were computed using the density functional theory/multireference configuration interaction (DFT/MRCI) method [14].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Epoxidation of coronene reduces the molecular symmetry, lifts the degeneracy of the HOMO/LUMO levels, and removes the symmetry-forbidden character of optical transitions. Concurrently, edge epoxidation induces a slight shift in the electron density of the FMOs toward the oxygen atom, which can trigger a redistribution of these orbitals across the entire conjugated framework. This reorganization modulates the spatial overlap integral, directly linking structural perturbation to transition probability. The spatial distribution of the HOMO and LUMO for coronene epoxidized at the α - and β -positions is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of the HOMO and LUMO for epoxidized coronene: (a) α -position, (b) β -position.

Furthermore, the change in hybridization state of the epoxidized carbon atoms can induce π -electron localization and disrupt π -conjugation within specific benzene rings. Such structural alterations can also influence the electron density distribution of the HOMO and LUMO. Notably, the degree of π -electron localization is directly governed by the attachment site of the functional group, which critically modulates the spatial overlap integral between the HOMO and LUMO wavefunctions. As demonstrated in our recent study [7], Clar's rule [15,16] serves as an effective tool for evaluating the impact of epoxidation on the structural features of coronene. The structures of epoxidized coronene, with aromatic sextets explicitly visualized, are presented in Figure 3. Aromatic sextets are denoted by circles.

Figure 3. Structures of epoxidized coronene: (a) α -position, (b) β -position. Aromatic sextets are denoted by circles.

As can be seen, epoxidation exerts a non-uniform influence on the structural and electronic properties of coronene. Consequently, the positions of absorption and emission bands, as well

as the oscillator strengths for the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transitions, differ markedly between the α - and β -epoxidized isomers. The absorption and fluorescence wavelengths, together with the corresponding oscillator strengths for pristine and epoxidized coronene, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Absorption and fluorescence wavelengths, together with oscillator strengths for pristine and epoxidized coronene isomers.

Structure	Singlet excited state	Absorption edge (nm)	Oscillator strength	Fluorescence (nm)	Oscillator strength
Pristine coronene	S1	404 (422*)	0.000	431 (428*)	0.000
Epoxy α	S1	390	0.002	414	0.002
Epoxy β	S1	446	0.310	574	0.231

* Experimental values taken from Ref. [17].

The reduction of the point group symmetry to C_{2v} upon α -epoxidation lifts the HOMO/LUMO degeneracy and induces a phase inversion in one of the frontier orbitals. Furthermore, the change in hybridization at the functionalized carbon atoms perturbs their electron density. However, this functionalization does not trigger substantial redistribution of the FMOs. These changes do not affect the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition, which remains forbidden ($f \approx 0.002$).

In contrast to the α -position, the epoxy group at the β -position exerts a substantial influence on the structural, electronic, and optical properties of coronene. Specifically, attachment of the epoxide moiety induces π -electron localization within the epoxidized ring and two adjacent benzene rings, thereby disrupting their π -conjugation. Concurrently, it leads to localization of the LUMO electron density on the oxygen atom and its adjacent bonds.

Taken together, these factors induce a more extensive redistribution of the FMOs compared to the α -position. As a result, the spatial overlap between the HOMO and LUMO wave functions for the dipole transition becomes more effective, leading to an increased transition dipole matrix element and, consequently, an enhanced oscillator strength for the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition.

It is important to note that coronene epoxidized at the β -position is metastable, as evidenced by the low activation barrier for its transformation into an ether bridge (≈ 0.1 kcal/mol in the S_0 state). Nevertheless, the present results successfully elucidate the mechanism of optical tuning in carbon nanostructures via epoxidation. It is demonstrated that the decisive factor is not the functionalization, but rather its specific impact on the electron density distribution.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that epoxidation disrupts π -electron delocalization and localizes electron density on the oxygen atom, inducing a position-dependent redistribution of the frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs). This electronic reorganization enhances the spatial overlap integral between the HOMO and LUMO wavefunctions, thereby increasing the transition dipole moment and, consequently, the oscillator strength of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition. A direct correlation was established between the degree of structural perturbation and FMO redistribution: pronounced disruption of the delocalized π -system yields highly efficient orbital overlap and a substantial enhancement of f , whereas minor geometric distortions preserve weak overlap and low transition probability.

The obtained results establish structure–property relationships that enable the controlled tuning of optical characteristics in symmetric PAHs and GQDs through targeted edge functionalization. However, pronounced disruption of the delocalized π -system, while enhancing the oscillator strength of optical transitions, may concurrently compromise the kinetic stability of the functionalized framework. It should be noted that generalization of these findings requires validation across an expanded set of model nanographenes with varying size and point-group symmetry.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, D.R. and I.E.; methodology, D.R. and I.E.; software, D.R. and I.E.; validation, D.R. and I.E.; formal analysis, D.R.; investigation, D.R. and I.E.; resources, I.E.; data curation, D.R.; writing—original draft preparation, D.R.; writing—review and editing, D.R. and I.E.; visualization, D.R. and I.E.; supervision, D.R.; project administration, D.R.; funding acquisition, A.L. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

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